

DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING OF OLDER PRESCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH DIDACTIC PLAY AND TRIZ TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation

This article contains methodological recommendations for the development of logical thinking of older preschool children through the use of didactic games and TRIZ technology as effective means of developing children's mental abilities. Specific examples of the implementation of gaming technology from the experience of the educator, various methods of motivating gaming activities with children and parents of pupils are given.

Key words

Technology, activity, development, experience.

The relevance of the development of cognitive abilities in preschool children is dictated by modern reality. We live in a rapidly changing world, in the era of information, computers, satellite television, mobile communications, and the Internet. Information technology gives us new opportunities. An interesting future awaits our students today. And in order for them to be successful, skillfully navigate the ever-growing flow of information, you need to teach them to easily and quickly perceive information, analyze it, apply it in mastering new things, find extraordinary solutions in various situations.

In accordance with modern trends in the development of education, we must let out of kindergarten a person who is inquisitive, active, takes a lively, interested part in the educational process, has the ability to solve intellectual and personal problems, and has mastered the universal prerequisites of educational activity. The role of logic in this case cannot be overestimated. In order for the student not to experience difficulties literally from the first lessons and he did not have to learn from scratch, already now, in the preschool period, it is necessary to prepare the child accordingly. Logical thinking rightfully occupies a very large place in the system of preschool education. It sharpens the child's mind, develops flexibility of thinking, teaches logic. Many people think that developed logical thinking is a natural gift, the presence or absence of which should be accepted. However, there are studies by well-known psychologists confirming that the development of logical thinking can and should be engaged in (even in cases where the natural inclinations of a child in this area are very modest).

Logical thinking is formed on the basis of figurative thinking and is the highest stage of development of children's thinking. Achieving this stage is a long and complex process, since the full development of logical thinking requires not only high activity of mental activity, but also generalized knowledge about the general and essential features of objects and phenomena of reality, which are fixed in words. The development of logical thinking should begin in preschool childhood. Having mastered logical operations, the child will become more attentive, learn to think clearly and clearly, will be able to concentrate on the essence of the

problem at the right moment, convince others of his rightness. It will become easier to study, which means that both the learning process and school life itself will bring joy and satisfaction.

The first assistant in the formation of logical thinking is a game – one of the most attractive activities for children. Logical games of mathematical content bring up children's cognitive interest, the ability to creatively search, the desire and ability to learn. Any logical task for ingenuity, for whatever age it is intended, carries a certain mental load, which is most often disguised by an entertaining plot, external data, the condition of the task, etc. The mental task: to make a figure or modify it, to find a solution, to guess a number – is realized by means of the game in game actions. Ingenuity, resourcefulness, initiative are manifested in active mental activity based on direct interest.

Also use the methods and techniques of TRIZ technology as an innovative means of developing logic and curiosity of a preschooler.

We, teachers, try to use among modern innovations in preschool education precisely those techniques and technologies that are not only effective, but also fascinating.

Realizing the importance of the above, I identified the topic of my work "The development of logical thinking of older preschool children through didactic games and TRIZ technology." Using logical-mathematical, didactic and TRIZ games as a means of activation in the formation of logical thinking, I set a goal.

Purpose: Development of cognitive activity, logical thinking, striving for independent cognition and reflection, development of mental creative abilities through didactic games and TRIZ technology.

Tasks:

1. Teach children to identify the essential features of objects, compare, generalize, classify on mathematical and life material.
2. To form and develop the simplest logical structures of thinking and mathematical representations.
3. Improve voluntary attention, memory.
4. Develop the ability to express the simplest of their own judgments and conclusions based on the acquired knowledge.
5. Develop creative and intellectual abilities through logical-mathematical, didactic, educational, TRIZ games for the development of spatial imagination.
6. Develop motivation to solve cognitive, creative tasks, to a variety of intellectual activities.
7. To foster the desire to acquire new knowledge and skills.

To solve the tasks, the following work was carried out:

- a corresponding developing environment has been created (a logical and mathematical corner has been created in the group, where educational games of logical content, individual handouts for the development of logical thinking are located);
- a model of the pedagogical process has been developed – an educational project for older preschool children "Reflect, develop logic for school";
- a card file of logical and mathematical games, didactic, educational, TRIZ games for the development of spatial imagination, creative thinking has been compiled;

- a folder with recommendations for parents on the need to develop logical thinking of preschoolers "Logical thinking of a preschooler", "Logical tasks for children 6-7 years old", "Where is logic? Getting ready for school", "How to play logic games at home?"

D/I "Why did this happen?", "What first, what then?";

Semantic correlation.

D / And "What fits", "Does it happen", "Both good and bad", inventing tall tales;

-viewing the pictures "Find the differences", "The fourth extra";

- reading entertaining questions;

- tasks – jokes;

- graphic dictation;

- participation in Olympiads for the development of mathematical abilities;

- KVN "Clever and clever", mathematical entertainment, creative tasks "Draw a guess to an invented riddle", "Make a riddle and draw it", "Come up with a code card".

For example, the plot – role-playing game "Pharmacy". The educator invites children to name their favorite vegetables and fruits, specifying where and how vegetables and fruits grow (on the code cards for fruits, an image of a tree is used, and for vegetables, an image of a garden). A code card is a recipe according to which a pharmacist dispenses a delicious medicine. For example: grows on a tree, round, not red and not yellow (this is a green apple, 8 card code).

Or the storytelling role-playing game "Shop".

The child buyer shows the seller a code card and asks him to find the right product according to the description.

For example: small, not round, green, edible is a cucumber.

Big, round, not red, not green, not orange and inedible – this is a drum.

In the process of completing tasks, students learn to observe, notice similarities and differences, notice changes, identify the causes of these changes, their nature and on this basis draw conclusions in the form of a proposal, that is, to put forward hypotheses. It must be remembered that thought is impossible without a question. The path from question to answer is the work of thought. The main thing here is not only to ask questions yourself, but to teach this to children. Every question of a child is an opportunity to teach him to reason, to doubt, to think, to try to find the answer himself. Pupils are easily involved in any activity, especially gaming, since the game is of exceptional importance: the game for them is study, the game for them is work, the game for them is a serious form of education.

When selecting and conducting logical and mathematical games (Appendix 2), the following conditions were taken into account: work with children should be carried out in the system, connect activities with work in everyday life, take into account the individual and physiological characteristics of children, use various forms of work (games, observations, leisure, etc.)

-So, a "Council of Sages" was created in the children's collective, whose meetings were held 1 time a week, starting with the greeting ritual and the motto of the sages. The educator, the Wisest Sage, addressed the young sages by name and patronymic, motivating the children to the educational process.

- The parents of the group sewed robes and made caps of scientists, which gave the meeting of the sages a special atmosphere. Children were more quickly involved in the plot of the game – the next meeting.

Lesson structure

— Warm-up

A warm-up in the form of a riddle, acquaintance with a fairy-tale character allows you to activate the attention of children, raise their spirits, helps to set them up for educational activities, for communication with a teacher.

—The main content of the lesson is the study of new material.

The main content of the lesson is a set of games and exercises aimed at solving the tasks of this lesson.

— Physical minute

Physical training allows children to relax, switch from one type of activity to another, promotes the development of large and small motor skills.

- Fixing of new material.

The consolidation of new material gives the teacher the opportunity to assess the degree of mastery of new knowledge by children.

The educational game, coloring a "smart" picture on the topic at the end of the lesson is a kind of reflection, the logical end of the work done and serve as an incentive for its continuation.

And, although the line for the development of logic and curiosity of preschoolers is quite evident in the manuals, there are a lot of exercises in them aimed at developing a system of cognitive actions and operations, however, my long-term pedagogical practice has shown that additional tasks are needed that require the application of knowledge in new conditions. And for this, I decided to try out all the known methods and techniques of TRIZ on a logic game. Using elements of TRIZ in my work with children, I try to implement the main credo of the Triz people: "Every child is initially talented and even brilliant, but he must be taught to navigate the modern world in order to achieve maximum effect with a minimum of costs" (G.S. Altshuller).

During the work of the project "Think, develop logic for school", I used various methods of TRIZ.

1. The method of focal objects of the Game: "Carousel", "Masha is confused", "Black and white", "Shifters", "Misrepresentation of fairy tales".
2. The method of contradictions of the Game: "Good - bad", "What does it look like?", "Fantasy", "What can be replaced?", "Magic houses"
3. The method of morphological analysis of the Game: "Auction", "Fantastic animal", "Was - became", "Everything in the world turned upside down"
4. The method of synectics of the Game: "Compose a riddle", "Lotto questions", "Logical chain", "Train of time", "Yes - no"

The pupils especially liked quest games, such as "Save the enchanted Princess", "Vovka in the Faraway Kingdom", "Fairy House".

The work on the chosen topic would not be so productive if it were not for the close cooperation with the parents of the group. Our parents have always been active participants in the life of children in preschool. A long-term plan of work with parents was developed, namely:

- Familiarization of parents with the content of the educational program of the project "Reflect, develop logic for school!".
- Parents' questionnaire "Logical thinking of a future first grader".
- Development of consultations for parents on this topic.
- Involvement of parents in the production of visual material (selection of illustrations, making homemade games for the development of logic).
- Recommendations on how to organize children's games at home using entertaining mathematical material (memos, booklets, the DOW website).
- Recommendations for parents on the use of literature, parent meetings.
- Trainings, a master class on making logic games with your own hands, joint games – classes with children and parents.
- The final game at the end of the school year "Where is the logic?" together with parents.
- among parents of the need to use entertaining mathematical material in the family in order to solve the problems of comprehensive development of children during preschool childhood, preparing them for school.

Working on the problem of developing logical thinking of older preschoolers, I came to the conclusion that the most effective means are didactic games, intellectual games and warm-ups, logical search tasks, game TRIZ exercises of an entertaining nature, the diverse presentation of which emotionally affects children. They activate children, because they have a change of activity: children listen, think, answer questions. During the game, various mental processes are activated, a creative original approach to solving problems is developed, the desire to be in search of a logical conclusion is brought up.

Thus, we can conclude that the pedagogical possibilities of logic games are very great. Games and exercises in logic develop all aspects of the child's personality, activate hidden mental and intellectual capabilities. Participation of preschoolers in didactic games promotes their self-affirmation, develops perseverance, striving for success and various motivational qualities. In TRIZ games, thinking, logic, imagination, speech, curiosity are improved, including actions for planning, forecasting, weighing the chances of success, choosing alternatives. All this will allow the child to study more successfully at school.

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